

**A SINGLE CASE STUDY OF ROLE OF LODHRADI LEPA IN
MANAGEMENT OF YUVANPIDIKA****¹Dr. Pragya Yadav, ²Dr. Avadhesh Kumar, ³Dr. Renu Patel**

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ABSTRACT

In our literature it is well quoted that beauty is a thing of joy. In this era everyone wants to look beautiful. Beauty is a quality that gives great pleasure especially when someone look at them. When human face having clear and radiant skin in its most natural form it gives lots of confidence and mental strength. Unfortunately, the face skin is affected by a most common skin disorder 'Acne Vulgaris' and its occurrence mainly in the adolescent ages. Acne Vulgaris is defined as a chronic inflammatory condition of the pilosebaceous follicles on the face and upper trunk, which develops into blackheads, papules, pustules and cysts and may leave scars upon resolution. Since adolescents of current generation are very conscious about their health, skin and beauty, they try to resolve this skin problem by using various cosmetic products

available in the market and as shown in the advertisements, which most of the times causes the Acne problem to exaggerate widely and sometimes side effects also occur. Yuvan Pidika simply refers to the disorder that usually occurs in the young aged people. Its one synonyms is Mukhadushika. Although it is briefly mentioned in our texts by Acharya Sushruta in nidana sthana, the symptoms closely resembles that of Acne Vulgaris describe in modern science. According to the Ayurveda, the management of Yuvan Pidika is by done by both

Shodhana and Shamana Chikitsa. One of the key external treatments used for acne is '*Lodhradi Lepa*' and it is believed to have a cooling and soothing effect on the skin, helping to decrease inflammation and overall health of the skin. So shaman chikitsa by lodhradhi lepa will be discussed in this article.

KEYWORDS: Yuvanpidika, Mukhdushika, Mukhalepa, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

Yuvanpidika in modern terminology called as acne vulgaris, is a most commonest skin disease that generally affects adolescents and young adults. According to Ayurveda texts, it is primarily a result of vitiation of doshas mainly Kapha, Vata, and Rakta (blood) and it is considered as disease under heading of Kshudra Roga (minor disease). Acharya Sushruta describes Yuvanpidika in 13th chapter kshudra rogadohikara of Nidana sthana. Other acharyas like sharanghar and bhavprakash also describes yuvanpidika in their text. Yuvan pidika is *Shalmali* thorn like *Pitika*(thorn of *salmaliamalabarica* like eruption) of face due to vitiation of *kapha*, *Vata*, and *Rakta*. These are painful and hard filled with fat found on the face of adults are called *Mukhdushika* or *Yuvanpidika*. This disease, causes disfigurement of the face. Lifestyle plays a significant role in both the development and management of Yuvanpidika. In recent years, there has been increasing recognition of the role of lifestyle factors in the development and exacerbation of acne. An imbalanced lifestyle characterized by poor diet, stress, late night sleep habit, and lack of hygiene is a major contributor to Yuvanpidika. Ayurvedic management emphasizes on Dinacharya (daily routine) and Ritucharya (seasonal regimen) to maintain doshic balance, promote skin health, and prevent recurrence.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Patient information

A 29 years old female patient visited OPD no.10 on date 09/09/2025 in Government Ayurveda college and hospital, Varanasi with chief complaint of acne over face with redness, pain and swelling since 2 months. The body weight was 60 kg. Her menstrual history is regular and she is not taking any medication. there was no history of thyroid diabetes mellitus or hypertension. Her vitals were within normal limits. On general examination, there was no pallor, icterus, clubbing of nails, oedema or lymphadenopathy noted.

Clinical Examination

A. Local Examination No CNS abnormalities noted on through examination.

B. General Examination General Condition- fair.

Blood Pressure -120/76 m m of Hg

Pulse Rate-76/min

Respiratory Rate -16/m in Systemic examination- No any deformity

C. Laboratory investigations

Haemoglobin-11.9 gm/dl

Total leucocytes count-7300 cells/mm³

Platelet count-314000 lac cells/mm³

Plasma glucose random-100 mg/dl.

INTERVENTION**1st Day**

The patient was given lodhradhi lepa applied with sambhag water. This lepa was prescribed to use it over clean at day time in anulom disha for 2 times daily in a week and applied all over face and remove it before drying. Along with this lepa patient was adviced to avoid spicy(atimadur ras) food and sugary food(atimadur ras)intake. Also patient adviced to clean face twice a day and daily bath.

2nd day-14th Day

Repeat the above mentioned procedure for 14 days continuously.

1st follow up

After Application of lepa on 21st day patient come to OPD no. 10 with moderate improvement in condition of acne vulgaris.

2nd follow up

On 28th day patient come to opd no. 10 with complete improve in condition of acne.

Diet

Patient was adviced to take a balanced diet and avoid high glycemic index food, spicy and fast food.

Activity

Advised to wash face twice a day, take bath daily, use clean bed sheet and pillows and sanitize mobile phone properly and donot prick pimple.

Ethical Consideration

The procedure was Conducted following ethical guidelines with informed consent from patient. The study adhered to the principles of the declaration of Helsinki.

RESULT

Mild changes in symptoms were noticed after treatment with lodhradhi lepa for short duration of 7 days. On first day, patient had swelling redness and pus filled pustules on both cheeks these symptoms somewhat reduced on 5th day. On 14th day her face looking more clear swelling and redness reduced patient is satisfied with use of lodhradhi lepa. on 2nd follow up acne redness swelling and pus filled cyst completely disappeared.

BEFORE TREATMEN**DISCUSSION**

Yuvanpidika is a disease which harms the beauty of the face. The incidence of Yuvanpidika is increasing all over the world due to faulty diet patterns, excessive use of chemical face products, hormonal changes. A balanced diet plan and following the Dinacharya can play a good role in the prevention and cure of Yuvanpidika. In the text of Ayurveda Pathya Aahar-Vihara, various types of Yoga, lepa, Dincharya, Ritucharya are described which have a good role in the prevention and management of Yuvanpidika. If someone adopts the diet pattern,

Dinacharya (lifestyle) according to the Ayurveda it can be helpful in decreasing the incidence of Yuvanpidika. In the text of Ayurveda formulations like lodhradhilepa are described which have very effective results on the Yuvanpidika. lodhradhilepa removes vitiated vata kapha rakta doshas. The ingredients used in lodhradhilepa is lodhra, dhanaya and vacha pacify the vitiated doshas and brought into the equilibrium state and effective against vata kapha rakta pathology of Yuvanpidika.

CONCLUSION

1. In recent times Yuvanpidika is the one of the most burning problems. It has been found that adolescents are mainly susceptible to Yuvanpidika. It seems that we need to reassess our
2. entire lifestyle if we want to prevent and manage Yuvanpidika. In Ayurveda Ahara, Vihara, Dinacharya, Ritucharya, Mukhlepa, are described which have a good role in prevention & cure of the Yuvanpidika. The prevention and management of Yuvanpidika can be done successfully by Ayurveda therapy. Moreover Ayurvedic treatments are safe & affordable by everyone.

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